

GOVAQUA policy matrix – Introduction

GOVAQUA Deliverable 2.1

Governance innovations for a transition to sustainable and equitable water use in Europe (GOVAQUA)

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Introduction

Over the past two decades, Europe has witnessed a concerning trend of escalating water scarcity and more frequent drought events and floods, with projections indicating a continuation of this trend into the future. Further, despite decades of efforts to curb pollution, the health of water ecosystems in Europe continues to decline. In particular, the intensification of drought frequencies and water scarcity has led to heightened competition for water resources, forcing difficult trade-offs between supplying sufficient clean water for human needs, supporting various economic sectors, and preserving water needs of the environment. This complex situation has prompted European water managers and policymakers to seek innovative governance approaches capable of addressing unsustainable water use and enhancing resilience to water scarcity and droughts.

The overarching objective of the GOVAQUA project is to identify, assess, develop, and validate innovative water governance approaches that accelerate the transition towards sustainable and equitable water use in Europe. This endeavor encompasses a spectrum of innovations, ranging from legal and regulatory measures to advancements in public and stakeholder participation, collaboration, economic and financial instruments, and digital tools. Part of the GOVAQUA research work aims to characterize and assess the legal and regulatory challenges, levers and good practice to support a transition towards sustainable and equitable water use, in particular by contributing to achieve the objectives and ambitions of the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD), the European Green Deal (EGD) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Sustainable water use can be defined as "The use of water that supports the ability of human society to endure and flourish into the indefinite future without undermining the integrity of the hydrological cycle or the ecological systems that depend on it" (Gleick, 2000). In other words, water use should be managed so that environmental, social, and economic needs can be met now but also in the future. Complementing this, equitable water use can be understood as the fair allocation of water between different users, regions, stakeholder, and communities. This could, for example, be understood as equity between different administrative regions or between upstream and downstream areas (Speed et al., 2013). Equitable water use ensures reasonable and sufficient access to water for both basic needs and sustainable development.

The EU's approach to managing water resources revolves around three complementary pillars:

- EU environmental legislation, such as the Water Framework Directive (WFD) (2000/60) and its daughter directives, the Nature Directives (92/43; 79/409), the Groundwater Directive (2006/118) and Floods Directive (2007/60) establish binding targets and requirements to preserve aquatic ecosystems and manage water resources sustainably.
- Policy initiatives like the European Green Deal and its various strategies (e.g. Biodiversity, Climate Adaptation and Farm-to-Fork strategies), Circular Economy Action Plan and related strategies. Also previous policies such as the Communication on water scarcity and droughts and the Roadmap to a resource-efficient Europe set out policy objectives, targets and priorities that are directly or indirectly relevant to address water stress.
- Sectoral policy instruments such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) may support more efficient water use, an adaptation of economic activities to available resources or the development of new water supply infrastructures.

With the WFD, the European Union has set ambitious targets for achieving sustainable water management and attaining good water status by 2027, goals which have been reinforced through the European Green Deal. Good status is assessed both from a qualitative and quantitative standpoint, with the objective to remove and reduce pollution on the one hand, and to ensure sufficient water supply for both humans and ecosystems on the other. The WFD specifically emphasizes the safeguarding of flow regimes to achieve good ecological status, encompassing low flows, high flows, and groundwater-surface water exchanges essential for protecting water-dependent ecosystems. To achieve these aims, Member States are required

to implement River Basin Management Plans and Programmes of Measures to protect and restore water bodies.

The 2020 Fitness Check of EU water legislation concluded that the WFD's objectives are still unmet, due to slow implementation, a lack of funding, and inadequate environmental targets in sectoral policies. In addition to pressures from pollution and hydromorphological changes, water abstraction is seen as an important challenge for freshwater in Europe, especially in light of intensified agriculture and energy production. Progress in curbing significant water abstractions and mitigating pressures on water body quality and hydromorphology has however been limited (EEA, 2024). Challenges persist in implementing effective measures within river basin management plans, including issues concerning capacity, enforcement, and investments (EC, 2019). Particularly, the slow progress in implementing ecological flows poses a significant obstacle.

Additionally, a lack of integration between water and sectoral policies has resulted in conflicting incentives and unsustainable economic development. Achieving transformative change demands greater attention not only to water-intensive sectors such as irrigated agriculture and hydropower but also to the broader value chains, like food and energy systems.

More recent policy documents have emphasized the need to address barriers to sustainable water management. The European Green Deal (EGD) recognizes the cross-cutting nature of water and thus promotes a systemic and integrated approach to sustainability. The EGD introduced a range of instruments relevant to water management, such as the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the Farm-to-Fork Strategy, the EU Adaptation Strategy, and more. The EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 includes a number of targets related to water, covering both quality and quantity aspects. For example, the strategy aims to "increase efforts to restore freshwater ecosystems and the natural functions of rivers" and to "restore at least 25,000km free flowing rivers" by 2030. With regards to water quantity and sustainable water use, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 calls to review water abstraction and impoundment permits to restore and preserve ecological flows. The EGD also supports renewable energy (including hydropower) as well as mobility and transport issues, with a shift of most inland freight transport from road to rail and waterways, which would have implications for water allocation planning in some Member States.

The EU Adaptation Strategy also recognizes the importance of protecting and restoring aquatic ecosystems like wetlands and coastal/marine ecosystems, as well as the role of blue-green infrastructure in increasing climate resilience. The strategy mentions that ensuring sustainable freshwater availability is fundamental to climate resilience and will require transformational changes across sectors. In addition, the strategy highlights the need to improve thematic plans, water resource allocation planning, and water permits to ensure sustainable water use across sectors and borders. Water efficiency is also mentioned, through water saving requirements and improved drought management plans, soil management, and land use. Finally, the Adaptation Strategy points to the need for a guaranteed stable and secure supply of drinking water by including climate risks in water management analysis.

Finally, the European Commission proposed a Water Resilience Initiative in 2023 which aims to ensure access to water for citizens, nature and the economy, tackle floods and droughts, and identify and assess how best to manage climate risks across EU policies (EC, 2023). Key aspects that the Water Resilience Initiative is expected to cover include the improvement of water efficiency (with measures to reduce water abstraction and/or consumption in various sectors), investing in water infrastructure, promoting sustainable water management practices (sustainable water use, pollution prevention, integrated water resource management) and supporting research and innovation.

Objective and scope of report

In the context of key EU policy initiatives described in the previous section, three themes of legal and regulatory nature with high relevance to sustainable and equitable water use in Europe and in the GOVAQUA Living Labs have been chosen for closer inspection in this report:

- The design and implementation of water allocation regimes (how to provide enough water for users within limits of system)
- The design and implementation of eflows policies and strategies
- The regulation of water value chains.

The three selected themes are key building blocks for increasing water resilience in Europe, as they address the integration of environmental needs into legal and policy frameworks on water use, the reconciliation of current and potential water uses and the role of corporate behaviour for sustainable water use.

The integration of ecological flows and water allocation mechanisms in water management systems present innovative approaches to managing water with the aim to enhance resilience. Ecological flow (eflow) is the amount of water required for the aquatic ecosystem to continue to thrive and provide the services we rely upon (Tharme, 2003). Water allocation mechanisms define who is allowed to access water, how much may be taken and when, how it must be returned, and the conditions attached to the use of the water (OECD, 2015). Ecological flows defined to sustain aquatic ecosystems provide ecological boundaries for water allocation regimes. The water allocation process must then harmonize the requirements of water users with these ecological limits. The integration of eflows in water allocation is therefore a crucial step for their implementation. Managing allocations for water resources also plays a crucial role in ensuring effective and equitable distribution of water as a common good. With the present report, GOVAQUA contributes to research needs on the design and implementation of regulations being used for water allocation and ecological flows in different European countries and can highlight areas where actions need to be strengthened.

The regulation of water-intensive value chains seeks to enhance the sustainability of corporations' water use, thus contributing to sustainable water management practices. A corporation's value chains consist of the activities it undertakes to transform raw materials and components into final products, and cover both the corporation's own activities as well as those of its suppliers (Bair, 2008; Salminen and Rajavuori, 2019). Value chains may be fully domestic or – more often – geographically split into the areas of many legal jurisdictions (Pedersen *et al.*, 2017). Through such value chains and the related trade and business relations, a corporation may have an impact on water use in other EU member states and beyond. Managing corporations' water-related value chains is a crucial step in promoting sustainable water use by corporations. Corporate water stewardship is “socially and culturally equitable, environmentally sustainable and economically beneficial water use, achieved through a stakeholder-inclusive process that includes both site- and catchment-based actions” (AWS, 2023). The present GOVAQUA report analyses the legal and regulatory approach to value chain management in different European countries particularly from the perspective of water.

A host of environmental and sectoral legislation and policies at EU and national level build the legal and regulatory framework of these three themes linked to water use regimes. The analysis of national policies on water allocation, eflows and water value chains focuses on the six countries of GOVAQUA Living Labs (France, Spain, Sweden, Finland, Romania, England in UK), where innovative governance approaches for sustainable and equitable water use are to be developed and tested.

The results of the analysis are presented in three distinct parts of the report, so that they can also be made available as separate reports to interested audiences. **Part A** reviews national water allocation policies. **Part B** reviews national eflows policies and strategies. **Part C** reviews regulations for value chains and sustainable water footprints.

Although the results are presented in three distinct parts, the analysis of regulations on water allocation, eflows and water value chains followed a similar methodology.

Methodology and structure

For each of the three themes (water allocation, eflows, water value chains), a structured template was developed to collect and examine information on the key elements of national policies, laws and regulations in France, Spain, Sweden, Finland, Romania, and England in UK. For the development of each template, a review of literature was carried out, including other material such as policy evaluation consultancy reports if available. Each template includes a different set of questions adapted to the details needed for the characterization and analysis of the policy and regulatory frameworks on the three different themes.

Each of the national templates on water allocation, eflows and water value chains regulations was filled in by national experts of the GOVAQUA project through desk-based review of documentation. Interviews with nine national experts from governmental bodies and agencies were carried out to complement the data collection. Interview questions were tailored to each national context, and they primarily concentrated on the design and implementation of water allocation mechanisms and eflows policies. Value chain questions proved to be challenging for national expert interviews due to the lack of mature policies and lack of national experts in this field in many countries.

The results of the analysis for each theme are presented in a similar manner in each of the three parts of the report. Each part starts with a review of key EU policies and EU-level discussions for the respective theme (water allocation, eflows, water value chains). Then, the overarching legal, regulatory and institutional settings are characterised in the six countries analysed. Based on the more descriptive chapters, concluding sections highlight key challenges in implementing regulatory regimes for water allocation, eflows and water value chains in Europe and conclude with avenues for further work on innovations and solutions that can facilitate future implementation.

Links to the GOVAQUA project

The current deliverable D2.1, which analyses national water allocation and eflows policies and regulations of value chains and sustainable water footprints, feeds directly into the first building block of the GOVAQUA project on the analysis of thematic water governance innovations (see Figure 1 below)). This analysis is closely linked to the other key building blocks of the project, as described in the figure.

The deliverable D2.1 has been developed in WP2 (legal and regulatory approaches) and is linked to all the other thematic work-packages of the project:

- It provides background information on legal and regulatory aspects of sustainable water use for the development and testing of the water governance assessment tool in WP1. It also contributes to the development of the overall GOVAQUA project recommendations on transitions to sustainable water governance in WP1.
- It provides a review of key legislation and policies as well as key policy implementation challenges in the domestic national context, as input to the groundwork setting of each of the GOVAQUA Living Labs in WP6.
- It provides direct input to the development of Policy Briefs in WP7 which target policy-makers, the river basin manager community as well as water use sectors in the context of the upcoming EU Water Resilience Strategy.

- It provides policy and legal contextual information for various case studies which will be developed in WP3, WP4 and WP5 respectively on participatory, economic and digital instruments for water governance.

Further work in WP2 will focus on collecting and assessing specific governance innovations and good practice related to the three themes (Task 2.2) and drawing policy recommendations to support the new water resilience agenda, as highlighted by the EEA’s recent State of Water report (EEA, 2024) and the political guidelines of the new EU Commission 2024-2029 (van der Leyen, 2024).

Figure 1. Positioning of the analysis of thematic water governance innovations, in WP2 the legal and policy analyses, in the overall framework of the GOVAQUA project.

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